

(a)

Peak pattern	mock		WT-F 3 h p.i.	
	no. clusters	no. genes	no. clusters	no. genes
One TSS peak	33	5728	21	3347
Additional minor peak downstream of major TSS peak	13	1461	17	2986
Two approximately equally high peaks	2	232	4	296
Additional downstream peak higher than TSS peak	0	0	7	834
none of the above	2	228	1	46

(b)

Fig. S7